
Differentiated Instruction in Physical Education and Students' Engagement in Dance Activities

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ABSTRACT: This study aimed to assess and explore the students' engagement in performing dance activities in a differentiated instruction of physical education among senior high school learners. Employing descriptive correlational research design, 51 STEM students from grade 12 responded to a survey questionnaire, which served as the main instrument in this study. The data gathered were subjected to descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation, and inferential statistical analysis, such as Pearson Correlation. This study revealed that Differentiated Instruction in Physical Education and the students' engagement in dance activities were effective in teaching Physical education including well-ventilated environment, employing variety of strategies for learner's development and progress. The engagement of the respondents in dance activities were determined in their learning styles, physical, emotional, and cognitive was practiced. The respondents observed strict compliance and attentiveness with their tasks. It was found out that Differentiated Instruction in Physical Education and the students' engagement in dance activities among senior high school students is practically effective especially in employing leadership strategies and collaborative attitude, it plays a vital role in developing work engagement among the learners for a good output. Though, still need to improve the use of differentiated instruction to make students fully engaged in physical education in dance activities.

KEYWORDS: dance activities, differentiated instructions, students' engagement

INTRODUCTION

The role of an educator as an integral part of the educational environment should ensure that they both find teaching a very rewarding career and understands how challenges are made to improve the delivery of instruction. Physical education is one of the core subjects to senior high school students where teachers are encouraged to not just meet the learning competencies but incorporate various tasks called differentiated instruction that will help the process in developing student's skills and potential.

Tomlinson (2021) believed that "Differentiated instruction is a philosophy of teaching purporting that students learn best when their teachers effectively address variance in students' readiness levels, interests, and learning profile references. A key goal of differentiated instruction is maximizing the learning potential of each student." "Teaching students to care about themselves and each other begins with providing the environment and the language they need to interact, both with students who are labeled and with those who are not."

Baglierei & Knoop (2014), suggested that teaching should be delivered in various methods such as whole group, small group and one on one. Teachers and students should fully understand and be able to articulate the learning goals for each lesson. Students should receive pre-assessments as well as formative assessments along the way. Flexibility is key and student/teacher relationships share the responsibility of respect and an optimal learning environment.

Thus, the researcher agreed that the underlying philosophy, studies, and observation toward differentiated instruction and its impact to highlight the transfer of learning as well as students' engagement are validation what a physical education teacher should be purposefully doing during their respective classes.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The purpose of the study aimed to assess students' engagement in performing dance activities in a differentiated instruction of physical education among Senior High School Students. It sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Age, and
 - 1.2. Sex?
2. How do the respondents perceive the components of differentiated instruction as to:

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- 2.1. Assessment,
- 2.2. Content, and
- 2.3. Process?

3. What is the level of engagement in dance activities of the respondents in terms of:

- 3.1. Intellectual Engagement.
- 3.2. Cognitive Engagement, and
- 3.3. Academic Engagement?

4. What is the performance of the respondents in dance activities using differentiated instruction?

5. Are the perceptions of the respondents on differentiated instruction significantly related to:

- 5.1. Engagement in dance activities; and
- 5.2. Performance?

Hypotheses of the Study

Based on the findings of the study, the following hypotheses were shown:

1. Perceptions of the respondents on differentiated instruction are not significantly related to their:
 - 1.1 engagement in dance activities; and
 - 1.2 performance

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research study utilized quantitative research employing descriptive correlational design with repeated measures design for the study. Repeated Measures design is an experimental design where the same participants participate in each independent variable condition. This means that each experiment condition includes the same group of participants. Repeated Measures design is also known as within-groups or within-subjects design. This method is found appropriate since it will use the questionnaire for both the control and experimental groups involved in applying differentiated instruction in dance activities and the students' engagement. This will assess the differentiated instruction and engagement of students in dance activities among Senior High School students.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were the fifty-one (51) STEM Senior High School students. This was found appropriate since they were the ones undergoing dance activities in the school. They were a diversity of learners in performing dance activities in physical education and their engagement with their teachers.

Research Instrument

The study used questionnaire as the main sources of data in the study. This is divided into three parts. The first part pertained to the profile of the respondents. The second part delved into the differentiated instruction in dance activities among Senior High School students. The third part discussed the students' engagement in dance activities among Senior High School students.

The questionnaire underwent two processes of validation - content validation where three experts of the field examined the questionnaire – One Doctor, One Master Teacher, and One English Teacher, and construct validation where at least thirty respondents answered but were not included in the actual data gathering stage. Cronbach Alpha was also applied for validity and reliability of the test items.

Sampling Technique

The respondents of this research study were chosen through simple random sampling technique. This method gave the respondents an equal and independent chance to become part of the study. This method involved lottery method, draw lots, and random selection of numbers. This was found appropriate since the study picked a number of fifty-one (51) STEM Senior High School students to solicit information about dance activities in a diverse learners' environment.

Research Procedure

The researcher asked the approval of the research adviser. She then prepared the rough draft of the questionnaire and the manuscript for checking and editing. The questionnaire was validated before distribution to the targeted respondents. The researcher used Google form in distributing the questionnaire or personally distribute the questionnaire to the targeted respondents. The first data gathering started with the distribution of the questionnaire before applying differentiated instruction in dance activities. The data were treated as the Control Group of the experimental study. And, the second round of distribution was after the differentiated instruction was applied in dance activities as taught to the STEM students. Here, the teacher or researcher gave a lecture on dance activity with the application of differentiated instruction. This was considered as the experimental group of the experimental study. Necessary results were tallied and tabulated.

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Statistical Treatment of Data

The following statistical tools were used to analyze and solve the problem of the study:

1. Frequency Count. This measured the profile of the respondents who participated in the conduct of the study.
2. Mean. This measured and computed the responses on the differentiated instruction students' engagement in dance activities among Senior High School students.
3. T-Test for Dependent/Paired/Correlated/Related Sample. Since the Likert Type questions were utilized in the study, t-Test for Dependent/Paired/Correlated/Related Sample was utilized to determine the significant difference.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Part 1. Profile of the Respondents

Table 1. Frequency Distribution of the Respondents' Profile

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
18-19	31	60.78
16-17	20	39.22
Total	51	100.00
Sex	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	23	45.10
Female	28	54.90
Total	51	100.00

The majority of the respondents were 18-19 years of age with a frequency of 31 (60.78%). The remaining respondents were 16-17 years of age having a frequency of 20, or 39.22%. Majority of the respondents were females with a frequency of 28 (54.90%). The remaining respondents were males having a frequency of 23, 45.10%.

Part 2. Level of Implementation of Differentiated Instruction of Students in Dance Activities

Table 2. Respondent's Assessment on the Differentiated Instruction in Dance Activities in terms of Assessment

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
pre-assess students before instructing.	4.73	0.57	Strongly Agree
pre-assess readiness to adjust the lesson.	4.45	0.67	Strongly Agree
assess during the unit to gauge understanding.	4.53	0.73	Strongly Agree
assess at the end of the lesson to determine knowledge acquisition.	4.39	0.80	Strongly Agree
determine students' learning styles.	4.51	0.76	Strongly Agree
Overall	4.52	0.58	Strongly Agree

Legend: "Strongly Disagree (1.00 – 1.50)", "Disagree (1.51 – 2.50)", "Fairly Agree (2.51 – 3.50)", "Agree (3.51 – 4.50)", "Strongly Agree (4.51 – 5.00)"

Table 2 showed the respondents' assessment on the differentiated instruction in dance activities among Senior High School students in terms of Assessment. The general mean was 4.52 with a verbal interpretation of "Strongly Agree." This implied that the respondents gave a strongly agreed rating on the assessment of the differentiated instruction in dance activities among Senior High School students.

The top scorer was the statement saying that "the respondents **pre-assess students before instructing**" with a mean rating of 4.73. This indicated that students were pre-examined in dance activities before lecture or instruction.

The lowest mean showed that "the respondents **pre-assess readiness to adjust the lesson**" with a mean of 4.45. This means that the teachers pre-examined the readiness of the students before application of differentiated instruction.

The above result is true in the study of Heritage, et al., (2019) which states that assessments are used throughout the implementation of DI and are the driving force behind the specific instruction provided.

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Table 3. Respondent's Assessment on the Differentiated Instruction in Dance Activities in terms of Content

Content	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
The curriculum is based on major concepts and generalizations.	4.52	0.58	Strongly Agree
It clearly articulates what the students want to know, understand, and be able to do.	4.59	0.70	Strongly Agree
Use variety of materials other than the standard text.	4.55	0.64	Strongly Agree
Provide a variety of support strategies (organizers, study guides, study buddies).	4.16	1.05	Agree
Overall	4.41	0.83	Agree

Legend: "Strongly Disagree (1.00 – 1.50)", "Disagree (1.51 – 2.50)", "Fairly Agree (2.51 – 3.50)", "Agree (3.51 – 4.50)", "Strongly Agree (4.51 – 5.00)"

Table 3 illustrated the respondents' assessment on the differentiated instruction in dance activities among Senior High School students in terms of Content. The general mean was 4.41 with a verbal interpretation of "Agree." This implied that the respondents gave an agreed rating on the assessment of the differentiated instruction in dance activities among Senior High School students.

The highest indicator stated that "the respondents **clearly articulate what they want students to know, understand and be able to do**" with a mean of 4.59. This showed that the teachers explained well the lessons and instructions to be given to their students particularly during dance activities. The least indicator stated that "the respondents provide a variety of support strategies with a mean of 4.16. This showed that the teachers incorporate to their dance lessons organizers, study guides, and study buddies whenever necessary to gain clear understanding of the lessons.

Data above is supported by Vygotsky's theory of understanding that a student who reaches an answer can help teachers understand the importance of content and process.

Table 4. Respondent's Assessment on the Differentiated Instruction in Dance Activities in terms of Process

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
The pace of instruction varies based on individual learner's needs.	4.45	0.64	Agree
It uses learner preference groups and/or learning preference centers.	4.37	0.85	Agree
Group students for learning activities is based on readiness, interests, and/or learning preferences centers.	4.24	0.79	Agree
The classroom environment is structured to support variety of activities including group and/or individual work.	4.47	0.70	Agree
Overall	4.59	0.67	Agree

Legend: "Strongly Disagree (1.00 – 1.50)", "Disagree (1.51 – 2.50)", "Fairly Agree (2.51 – 3.50)", "Agree (3.51 – 4.50)", "Strongly Agree (4.51 – 5.00)"

Table 4 revealed the respondents' assessment on the differentiated instruction in dance activities among Senior High School students in terms of Process. The general mean was 4.59 with a verbal interpretation of "Agree." This implied that the respondents gave an agreed rating on the assessment of the differentiated instruction in dance activities among Senior High School students.

The top indicator stated that "the classroom environment is structured to support a variety of activities including group and/or individual work" with a mean of 4.47. This indicated that variety of activities were applied in the school.

The bottom indicator showed that "the respondents group students for learning activities based on readiness, interests, and/or learning preferences" with a mean of 4.24. This showed that the teacher group students based on learning activities based on readiness, interest, and/or learning preferences.

The above table is also related to the study of Pritchard, et al., (2015) that claimed about student's fitness education with an aim to measure and increase scores in fitness levels, knowledge, and physical activity.

Part 3. Students' Engagement in Dance Activities among Senior High School Students

Table 5. Respondent's Level of Engagement in Dance Activities as to Intellectual

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
The students tend to volunteer and answer the teachers' questions, bring new ideas, and enjoy discussions and debates.	4.42	0.61	Often Engaged
The students tend to observe, memorize, and accurately repeat dance movements.	3.96	0.72	Often Engaged

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The students tend to think, ask questions, and demand detailed explanations of unknown issues (exercises and movements).	4.31	0.73	Often Engaged
The students tend to think associatively and compare difficulties of movements.	4.20	0.69	Often Engaged
The students tend to actively and flexibly apply existing knowledge, and motor skills to new movement exercises.	4.25	0.72	Often Engaged
The students regularly find more information about new techniques and movements to supplement knowledge.	4.29	0.67	Often Engaged
Overall	4.25	0.63	Often Engaged

Legend: "Never Engaged (1.00 – 1.50)", "Barely Engaged (1.51 – 2.50)", "Sometimes Engaged (2.51 – 3.50)", "Often Engaged (3.51 – 4.50)", "Always Engaged (4.51 – 5.00)"

Table 5 showed respondents' assessment of the students' engagement in dance activities among Senior High school Students in terms of Intellectual Engagement. The general mean was 4.25. This implied that the respondents often engaged on the students' engagement in dance activities among Senior High School students.

The highest response stated that "the students tend to volunteer to answer teachers' questions, bring new ideas, and enjoy discussions and debates" with a mean of 4.42. while the lowest response showed that "the students tend to observe, memorize and accurately repeat movements" with a mean of 3.96 which is reflected to Physical and social environment combined with an interaction of behavior and biology are among the salient determiners of an individual's health and school provides both a physical and social environment for a student (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, 2010).

Table 6. Respondent's Level of Engagement in Dance Activities as to Cognitive

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
Physical Education is the best means to boost health.	4.26	0.53	Often Engaged
Physical Education helps students improve their own motor skills.	4.55	0.67	Often Engaged
Physical Education makes students to form the healthy habit of regular exercise and playing sports.	4.61	0.60	Often Engaged
Physical Education directs students to a healthy lifestyle, away from social vices.	4.57	0.70	Often Engaged
Physical Education is a means for students to practice their will, discipline, perseverance, and patience.	4.53	0.73	Often Engaged
Physical Education is a means to communicate with the community and society.	4.47	0.78	Often Engaged
Overall	4.33	0.82	Often Engaged

Legend: "Never Engaged (1.00 – 1.50)", "Barely Engaged (1.51 – 2.50)", "Sometimes Engaged (2.51 – 3.50)", "Often Engaged (3.51 – 4.50)", "Always Engaged (4.51 – 5.00)"

Table 6 shows the respondents' assessment of the student's engagement in dance activities among Senior High school Students in terms of Cognitive Engagement. The general mean was 4.33 with a verbal interpretation of "Often Engaged."

The top scorer stated that "PE helps students form the healthy habit of regular exercise and playing sports" with a mean of 4.61. This indicated that physical education form part in the healthy habit of dance exercise or playing sports. The bottom scorer showed that "PE is the best means to boost health" with a mean of 4.26. This indicated that physical education is the way of being physically fit and healthy. Sallis et al., (2012) mentioned the benefits of physical activity at schools. They identify PE course as HOPE (Health Optimizing Physical Education) and accentuate its role in developing knowledge, skills, abilities, and confidence for being physically active and for fighting obesity epidemic.

Table 7. Respondent's Level of Engagement in Dance Activities as to Academic

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
The students help to concentrate and listen to lectures during class time.	4.35	0.77	Often Engaged
The students tend to participate in all learning activities (expressing opinions, taking notes, participating in group games, etc.)	4.27	0.80	Often Engaged
The students are determined to overcome difficulties and complete all the assigned tasks.	4.41	0.78	Often Engaged
The students become self-disciplined, and practice after school hours.	4.47	0.73	Often Engaged
The students attend Physical Education classes on time.	4.47	0.67	Often Engaged
The students strictly comply with regulations in the examination.	4.41	0.70	Often Engaged
Overall	4.41	0.60	Often Engaged

Legend: "Never Engaged (1.00 – 1.50)", "Barely Engaged (1.51 – 2.50)", "Sometimes Engaged (2.51 – 3.50)", "Often Engaged (3.51 – 4.50)", "Always Engaged (4.51 – 5.00)"

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Table 7 shows the respondents' assessment on the students' engagement in dance activities among Senior High school Students in terms of Academic Engagement. The general mean was 4.41 with a verbal interpretation of "Often Engaged." This implied that the respondents often engaged on the students' engagement in dance activities among Senior High School students. The highest mean was "the students tend to be self-discipline, actively practice more after school hours" and "the students attend PE classes fully and on time" with the same means of 4.47. This indicated that the students are disciplined, and practice their piece at the end of class hours. This also showed that physical education classes were attended by the students. The lowest mean was "the students tend to enthusiastically participate in all learning activities (expressing opinions, taking notes, participating in group games, etc.)" with a mean of 4.27.

The current research landscape on PE course seems fragmented. Much research focuses on development of young athletes from stakeholders' points of view (Kristiansen & Houlihan, 2017).

Part 4. Performance of the Respondents in Dance Activities using the Differentiated Instruction

Table 8. Performance of the Respondents in Dance Activities using the Differentiated Instruction

Score	Rating	F	%	Verbal Interpretations
17-20	Above 89	29	56.86	Excellent
13-16	85-89	22	43.14	Very Good
9-12	80-84	-	-	Good
5-8	75-79	-	-	Fair
0-4	70-74	-	-	Poor
Total		51	100.00	

Table 8 showed the performance of the respondents in dance activities using differentiated instruction. Majority of the respondents above 89 average which is verbally interpreted as excellent. This was followed by those 85-89 average interpreted as very good. This indicated that the students are at par in their physical education academic performance.

Ryan, (2018) and Millslaglem & Morley, (2014) describes the role conflict that can affect the teacher adversely in either role and can create what is known as role retreatism. The pressure that full-time teachers or coaches face has frequently been researched to identify the underlying causes of stress between the two roles of teaching and coaching Primary stressors are the main factors that lead to what is known as role retreatism. In addition, time, enjoyment, role overload, role expectancies, distinct and differing reward systems, differing sport experiences, unavoidable conflict situations, role stress and resentment and polarization between coaches and non-coaching personnel within an educational organization contribute to stress.

Part 5. Significant Relationship Between the Perceptions of the Respondents on Differentiated Instruction and their Performance

Table 9. Significant Relationship Between the Perceptions of the Respondents on Differentiated Instruction to Student Engagement and Performance

Correlations	Students' Engagement			
	Intellectual Engagement	Cognitive Engagement	Academic Engagement	Performance
Assessment	0.376**	0.645**	0.636**	0.509**
Content	0.415**	0.715**	0.676**	0.562**
Process	0.408**	0.716**	0.727**	0.578**

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Table 9 highlighted the significant relationship between the perceptions of the respondents on differentiated instruction to their performance. Based on Differentiated Instruction variables such as assessment, content, and process as compared to students' engagement like intellectual, cognitive, and academic engagement, the correlation is significant at 0.01 level.

Moreover, based on Differentiated Instruction variables such as assessment, content, and process as compared to performance, correlation is also significant at 0.01 level.

Student's engagement as to intellectual, cognitive, and academic were found significant using differentiated instruction focusing on assessment, content, and process since the respondents are fully aware of its benefits – they will be more encouraged to improve their skills, become active in class discussion, and be part of breaking the stigma about the subject that only require them to perform to obtain grades.

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Summary of Table According to Sub-Variables

Level of Implementation of Differentiated Instruction of Students in Dance Activities	Average Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal interpretation
<i>Respondent's Assessment on the Differentiated Instruction in Dance Activities in terms of Assessment</i>	4.52	0.58	Highly Observed
<i>Assessment on the Differentiated Instruction in Dance Activities in terms of Content</i>	4.41	0.83	Observed
<i>Respondent's Assessment on the Differentiated Instruction in Dance Activities in terms of Process</i>	4.59	0.67	Highly Observed
Students' Engagement in Dance Activities among Senior High School Students	Average Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal interpretation
<i>Respondent's Level of Engagement in Dance Activities as to Intellectual</i>	4.25	0.63	Observed
<i>Respondent's Level of Engagement in Dance Activities as to Cognitive</i>	4.33	0.82	Observed
<i>Respondent's Level of Engagement in Dance Activities as to Academic</i>	4.41	0.60	Observed
Performance of the Respondents in Dance Activities using the Differentiated Instruction	Frequency	Percentage (%)	
<i>Performance of the Respondents in Dance Activities using the Differentiated Instruction</i>	51	100	

Legend: "Not Observed (1.00 – 1.50)", "Fairly Observed (1.51 – 2.50)", "Moderately Observed (2.51 – 3.50)", "Observed (3.51 – 4.50)", "Highly Observed (4.51 – 5.00)"

The above illustration brought the impression that Physical Education teachers should continue in recalibrating their ways to improve the delivery of instruction provided in the goals behind differentiated activities that matches the capacity of every learner. It should also be done with respect to the learning competencies of the subject. Teachers and students must meet at the core objectives in order to be able to achieve good result.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings derived, the following conclusions were drawn:

Differentiated Instruction variables such as assessment, content and process as compared to students' engagement like intellectual, cognitive, and academic engagement, correlation is significant at 0.01 level, thus rejecting the null hypothesis. There exists a significant relationship between differentiated instruction and student engagement. Moreover, based on Differentiated Instruction variables compared to performance, correlation is also significant at 0.01 level. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. There exists a significant relationship between the perceptions of the respondents on their differentiated instruction to their performance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the conclusions drawn, the following were recommended:

1. School administrators must provide variety of support strategies (organizers, study guides, study buddies) to maintain and strengthen the application of differentiated instruction in dance activities among Senior High School students.
2. Physical Education Teachers should improve the use of differentiated instruction to make students fully engaged in physical education in dance activities. They should be vigilant in every student's learning style, implement differentiated instruction into the physical education setting which include consistency, planning a program using cooperative group learning, and use of focus activities at the start of classes.
3. Senior high school learners must be able to communicate with their teachers in terms of skills and capacities that relates to the topic and be able to contribute to successful delivery of instruction.
4. Future Researchers should consider having a parallel study focusing on male learners where their teachers applied differentiated instruction to physical education lessons

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